

Leveraging Knowledge for Explainable AI in Personalized Cancer Treatment: Challenges and Future Directions

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Abstract

The rapid expansion of disease-specific knowledge poses challenges for clinicians to remain up-to-date and effectively leverage emerging information into clinical practice. Addressing this challenge requires implementation of an informed, evidence-based decision-support system continuously maintained and updated to align with the latest clinical guidelines supporting personalized decision-making in real-time. Knowledge graphs have emerged as data models, integrating multi-modal (multi-omics) data sources and representing them as interconnected networks. These graphs offer a framework which easily streamlines the iterative learning process for AI models facilitating transparency and explainability of complex interactions and interdependencies. In this paper, we discuss the major components, challenges and future directions of an explainable AI-supported system in the biomedical domain emphasizing its transformative potential for the healthcare system. We discuss the concept of modular multi-tiered AI-supported system architecture, data privacy and security issues along with existing technical barriers that should be overcome to develop an AI-driven decision support system capable of handling the complexity of multi-modal data, being adaptable to new knowledge and constantly evolving treatment guidelines. Finally, we showcase ongoing efforts by the Knowledge at the Tips of your Fingers (KATY) consortium to implement AI-assisted strategies for enhancing the contribution of -omics studies in personalized medicine.

Keywords: personalized medicine, knowledge graphs, explainability, AI, foundation models, clinical decision-making, multi-tiered technology

Introduction

There is an increasing interest in integrating diverse types of patient data, including genetic information, expression profiles, and lifestyle factors, into a unified, interconnected framework [1,2]. Leveraging this knowledge with AI models can provide clinicians with a comprehensive understanding of a patient's trajectory, enabling a transition from a one-size-fits-all solution to more personalized diagnosis and treatment [3, 4]. However, the rapid expansion in disease-specific knowledge poses challenges for clinicians, making it difficult to remain up-to-date and effectively incorporate emerging information into evidence-based treatment decisions. In an interconnected world, optimal patient outcomes could eventually be achieved through comprehensive patients' monitoring and integration of all relevant data allowing for personalized treatment adjustments. Addressing this challenge requires the implementation of informed, evidence-based decision-making in clinical practice supported by advanced software solutions, which are regularly maintained and updated to align with the latest clinical practice guidelines [5]. To support this vision of precision medicine, several tools have emerged.

IBM Watson for Oncology (WFO) was the first knowledge-based system leveraging natural language processing (NLP) assisting physicians in providing evidence-based treatment decisions. These decisions were categorized as *recommended*, *for consideration*, or *not recommended* across seven types of cancer. WFO was designed to bridge the gap between clinical practice and academic research introducing the latest clinical evidence into informed decision-making. Alongside the NLP-driven WFO, OncoDoc2 emerged as a decision-tree-based system designed to integrate clinical data from electronic health records (EHR), assisting in selecting optimal treatments for non-metastatic breast cancer [6]. Similarly, a guideline-based decision support system was developed as part of the DESIREE European project, which aimed to create web-based services for managing primary breast cancer [7,8].

In the field of medical image analysis including X-rays, CT images, and MRI scans, deep learning techniques have significantly enhanced tumor detection, localization, assessment of muscle invasiveness and tumor grading. These advancements facilitated the distinction between disease subtypes enabling more effective treatment planning [9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16]. As an example, a 3D deep radiomics pipeline has been successfully used for analyzing CT scans of metastatic urothelial cancer patients, demonstrating capability of differentiating between disease, control and progression in response to immunotherapy with a predictive accuracy of 82.5% [17].

While creating a straightforward decision support system is technically feasible, a key challenge lies in translating the outcomes of complex AI-driven data integration and modeling into a form which is easily understood by the clinical audience and compliant with binding legal provisions. To address this challenge, efforts are focused on integrating medical knowledge, biological pathways, and clinical guidelines into knowledge-based models. By encapsulating the available knowledge into a knowledge graph (KG) and incorporating it into the AI model architecture, it is possible to provide explainable visualizations of the model's

complex reasoning enhancing AI-supported, knowledge-based diagnosis and treatment recommendations within a specific biomedical domain [arXiv:2310.13767v2]. From a technical viewpoint, complex inferences arise from AI model architectures where compressed feature spaces are trained to cluster datasets in a more-or-less unsupervised way. To draw patients-oriented insights from such a complex space, an effort should be made towards prioritizing the aggregation of similar patient trajectories that include clinical metadata as well as rich molecular profiling datasets. While developing such AI-supported clinical decision-support systems is achievable, adding an explainability component that translates to interpretability remains a significant challenge for real-world implementation.

However, AI-driven clinical decision support systems will not be shaped by technology alone. It will require constant collaboration and effort of medical professionals, software developers, and the research community to address emerging challenges in real-time. Successful cooperation of different professionals has then a chance to contribute not only to the promotion of personalization in the healthcare domain, but can also lead to a paradigm shift of how healthcare is perceived, administered, and experienced. Shifting towards personalization will inevitably enhance disease diagnosis and treatment and is a step forward to forecast a patient's health trajectory, thereby aiding preventive medicine [18].

In this paper we describe major components, challenges and future direction upon developing a multi-tiered AI-supported system in the biomedical domain and assess its transformative potential for healthcare. As an example of such a decision-support system under development, we present the ongoing efforts of the Knowledge at the Tips of Your Fingers (KATY) project consortium towards treating clear cell renal cell carcinoma (ccRCC).

Major components of explainable AI-supported systems

Knowledge-based models

Integrating various multi-modal biomedical data sources into a unified knowledge-based model begins with developing ontologies, which are structured frameworks for organizing information that define the relationships between key concepts and categories within a specific domain. These ontologies establish a formalized vocabulary, hierarchy of terms, relationships and rules to describe large volumes of heterogeneous biomedical data. Building on this foundation, knowledge graphs are constructed to integrate and represent diverse data sources as a network of interconnected entities (nodes) and relationships (edges). In this form, the KG is capable of capturing dynamic, real-world interactions and associations [19]. When tailored to a specific biomedical domain, KGs enhance data accessibility, interoperability, and integration, facilitating more efficient data analysis and further interpretation.

A key challenge in building KGs is the scattered and inconsistent nature of information across disease-specific domains. In cancer field, despite significant efforts made by consortia to develop standardized datasets, information from various organizational levels of datasets is dispersed across studies, unstandardized data repositories, evolving ontologies, and the need to continuously adapt to ever-changing clinical guidelines [20] which adds more complexity to harmonization and integration of diverse data sources. Building cohesive and functional knowledge graphs for cancer research faces several challenges related to: (i) Scalability - developing KGs requires manual labor and expensive expert input, making it difficult to scale; (ii) Variation in Cancer Representation Across Biomedical Data Repositories - cancer descriptions in medical repositories often do not follow standardized naming conventions or alignment with clinical guidelines, complicating large-scale data harmonization which hinders its usability and interoperability; and (iii) Ambiguity in Distinguishing Cancer Types - symptoms, causes, and manifestations of various cancers often overlap, making precise categorization of subtypes challenging.

Despite those difficulties, there have been constant efforts in building knowledge graphs from biomedical literature and clinical records. The Human Diseases Network (HDN) and Human Symptoms-Disease Network (HSDN) [21] have demonstrated the utility of disease-centric knowledge graphs via exploring the intricate relationships between clinical symptoms and diseases through molecular interactions enabling exploration of disease taxonomy and pathogenesis. The Scalable Precision Medicine Open Knowledge Engine (SPOKE) [22] has linked various biomedical databases to support precision medicine. By integrating individual patient data, SPOKE was capable of providing more personalized and data-driven healthcare insights. More recently PrimeKG, which is a multimodal KG for precision medicine has been developed offering a comprehensive and multi-modal view of diseases incorporating disease-associated perturbations in the proteome, biological processes, molecular pathways as well as anatomical and phenotypic scales, environmental exposures, and a range of approved and experimental drugs along with their therapeutic actions.

PrimeKG is designed to support AI models in understanding how drugs target disease-specific molecular perturbations [20]. Unlike the broad disease- or drug-oriented KGs, the Genetic and Rare Diseases Information Center (GARD) [23] focuses exclusively on rare diseases, aiming to advance understanding of unmet clinical needs and evidence-based research.

Currently, over a thousand biomedical ontologies are emerging in BioPortal [24] - a comprehensive repository covering various cancer fields such as breast, thyroid, and prostate cancer. Despite their availability, leveraging these ontologies effectively remains challenging. Many were developed with a specific perspective and purpose in mind tailored to specific research goals or projects, which may not align with other use cases or compatibility with new applications. Scientific institutions tend to fund specific projects not the platforms, so the developed ontologies often cease to be actively maintained or updated, which can quickly render them useless and at the same time contributing to the emergence of many new highly specific ontologies. To avoid perpetuating this trend, it is crucial to design ontologies with broader applicability and cross-domain compatibility. Prioritizing reusability and long-term maintenance can prevent the creation of isolated, short-lived frameworks and improve interoperability across research domains.

In addition to existing disease-focused ontologies, there is a growing interest in building stage- and grade-specific ontologies aimed at deeper conceptualizations of a specific disease, however this concept has not been explored much in biomedical domains. Also, transferring the knowledge embedded in KGs for the identification and characterization of rare disease is also of interest. Nowadays, research in the rare diseases field is oriented towards the collection and analysis of omics data in case-study scenarios. Adoption of the KG could interconnect between several studies, synthesizing state-of-the-art knowledge and providing greater explainability of rare diseases not only to clinicians and patients but also generally to the field. The adoption of a KG with its explainability hidden behind could provide more understanding of disease-specific feature importance leading to faster diagnosis, improved prognosis and clinical guidelines standardization.

Developing a detailed, domain-specific knowledge model embeds prior knowledge within the links and relationships between entities represented in a knowledge graph. By leveraging knowledge graphs, the learning process for AI models can be streamlined, enhancing explainability and transparency. This, in turn, improves interpretability [25], as knowledge graphs provide an initial framework that AI models can further refine. Complex neural network architectures naturally form graph-like structures, as entities encoded within these networks are interrelated. The AI model's weights can refine ontologies and highlight the most influential features and relationships in an interactive cycle. Upon AI model learning, the refined knowledge graph would incorporate new information while eliminating inconsistencies, redundancies and duplicates. As a result, this iterative process would improve the detection of patterns and correlations, identification of broader categories or clusters within the data that have not been immediately apparent.

This interplay between the knowledge graph and the AI model would definitely support more robust AI-driven insights and decision-making and is especially important for developing recommendation systems which should ideally be responsive and adaptive to real-

time changes introduced to the knowledge graph in real time. In order to achieve this, we need a constant refinement of the knowledge graph by a domain expert who is constantly supported by physician feedback. This mutual collaboration ensures the decision-support system is explainable, usable, transparent and aligned with current clinical needs. We believe that understanding the reasoning behind AI-assisted predictions will build trustworthiness across the medical community and additionally, upon confronting the clinician's knowledge with the knowledge learned by AI models we can possibly reduce the knowledge gaps and biases between humans and AI systems.

We believe that continuous interaction between physicians and AI provided by the system's architecture, along with dynamically curated databases and ongoing feedback from doctors, is essential for ensuring evidence-based, data-driven and research-supported recommendations for specific disease areas.

Enhancing explainability and interpretability of AI-supported models

Understanding the underlying mechanisms of the predicted condition and distinguishing meaningful predictions from spurious correlations across multiple data organizational levels is essential for AI-assisted scientific discovery.

We are at a turning point in history as advanced generative AI tools, such as ChatGPT and other large-scale models based on natural language processing, are being developed. What is being learned through the development of these tools is that to solve simple problems, such as filling in missing information, AI systems must develop an understanding of the solution they are creating. This understanding is embedded within the weights of large neural networks and the lower-dimensional space embeddings used by these models. Furthermore, the interpretability of these models is enhanced by techniques such as (i) attention mechanisms, which allow the model to focus on relevant parts of the input data, and (ii) explainable AI (XAI) methods, which help to elucidate how the AI system derives its conclusions. These advances are not only improving the accuracy and reliability of AI systems but are also making them more transparent and trustworthy for clinical use.

Explainability in AI or, more precisely, in machine learning approaches can generally be provided by (i) algorithms which are interpretable-by-design (white-box models, e.g. decision trees, linear models, and genetic programming models), which are transparent and capable of providing their own explanations to what the model computes, and (ii) algorithms considered black-box models (support-vector machines, artificial neural network-based models, probabilistic network-based models), which require post-hoc explainability provided by text explanations, visual explanations or feature relevance explanations [26]. Both approaches are characterized by advantages and weaknesses. The main advantages of white-box models are their transparency and ability to provide feature importance, which enhances explainability and interpretability. Disadvantages of these models relate to a risk of fitting on irrelevant features when the data is noisy, which potentially limits their predictive performance. Black-box approaches excel at handling data complexity and intricate patterns across different organizational levels, but they face weaknesses such as a lack of explainability and transparency, which makes understanding the reasoning behind their predictions challenging [27].

When dealing with unstructured multi-modal data, black-box models with more free parameters are preferred for capturing complex relationships in labeling, clustering, and pattern recognition tasks. In this form, they presumably enhance the global understanding of the system and its outputs, but do not provide explanations. To ensure explainability of the black-box model we need additional guidance from the domain knowledge a human expert can perceive, comprehend and understand [28] and we need to allow human experts to evaluate different models of explainability [29]. Therefore explainability and further interpretability of black-box algorithms is currently the biggest challenge upon bringing AI-based models into real-life applications.

To date, one study has utilized the knowledge graph fed with multi-source clinical data including basic clinical data, disease history, medical test results, and other Diabetic Macular Edema-related factors to predict this disease. The disease prediction model based on

improved correlation enhancement gained a precision rate of 86% while predicting this disease [30].

In the field of precision radiotherapy, the study by Niraula et al. developed a clinical decision support system leveraging knowledge-based AI-assisted decision-making in response-adaptive radiotherapy (ARClIDS). The system was designed to adjust optimal daily dosage of radiation to maximize the tumor local control probability and minimize the side effect. The novelty of the ARClIDS lied in capability of addressing not only anatomical changes related to treatment (weight loss, tumor regression, reductions in the volume of surrounding normal tissue, organs at risk) but also incorporating multi-omics data (clinical, dosimetric, radiomics, molecular biomarkers such as genomics (single nucleotide polymorphisms), transcriptomics (micro-RNA), and proteomics (cytokines)). This sequential decision-making system was the first web-based software with GUI dedicated to assist knowledge-based response-adaptive radiotherapy with multi-omics data improving the outcomes in dynamic treatment regime [31].

The study by Pfeifer et al. developed the Greedy Decision Forest, an explainable machine learning model handling multi-modal data for identifying disease modules. The model was trained on TCGA data using a node feature importance score based on SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) enhancing the interpretability of the Greedy Decision Forest approach. A key aspect of this approach was the iterative reduction of the number of considered features, which not only reduced computational costs but also provided reduced space of the model's interpretations. This methodological refinement highlighted the potential of the Greedy Decision Forest for biomedical knowledge discovery and decision-making [32].

In the realm of generating multi-level biomedical data, the development of AI solutions for personalized cancer treatment continues to face the persistent challenge of data sparsity. Despite constantly adjusting medical practice standards, the data will always be sparse, especially in the clinical trial context where primary focus is on the patient's health and not the amount of data generated. The exact sufficient data is generated to address a specific clinical question at hand, which from computational perspective means that simpler transparent models are often the most appropriate. Thus, perhaps a more modern approach would be to leverage foundation models – large, pre-trained AI models for specific data types that can be fine-tuned for specific tasks across various data types – and use them in black-box models with post-hoc explainability rooted in visual representation and feature relevance as a promising direction for introducing AI-supported systems to the medical community. While efforts towards building AI-supported decision systems in medical domains have been undertaken, a systematic study of the structure of explanations for decisions within disease-specific domains is still missing. The explanations provided must offer understandable and conceptually coherent knowledge. Only then can these models provide transparent, human-interpretable explanations of AI-assisted diagnosis and treatment recommendations, facilitating their adoption in real clinical settings. Building on how the AI model explains its predictions is crucial for gaining trust from the medical community and establishing domain-expert interpretation and inference grounded in current medical findings [33,34]. Because of data sparsity, these foundation models will need to leverage knowledge from publicly available omics data repositories and build knowledgeable databases within the context of

specific diseases. Addressing these gaps in explanation structure and data leveraging is essential for advancing knowledge-based model development and driving explainable AI.

To the best of our knowledge, there is no single study which tackles those missing aspects of explainable AI, or in other words, no study has utilized a knowledge graph-based explainable AI pipeline that integrates foundation models of omics data: genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, to enhance diagnosis and/or treatment decision-making within the sparse data context in a specific biomedical domain. In a real-world scenario, clinical decisions are largely driven by physicians' professional experiences, which may often differ significantly regionally. Thus, there is an urgent need for a system that can accommodate variations in professional experiences and local practices via building contextual explanatory models for real-world clinical settings. This effort has been undertaken by the *Knowledge at the Tips of your Fingers* (KATY) consortium funded in the H2020-EU.3.1. - SOCIETAL CHALLENGES - Health, demographic change and well-being programme under a call “*AI for Genomics and Personalized Medicine*” aims at implementing AI-assisted strategies for enhancing the contribution of -omics studies in personalized medicine.

Effort of the KATY consortium towards explainable AI

The KATY project develops a non-linear expert system capable of utilizing incomplete multi-modal omics information to predict the optimal treatment scheme in patients with metastatic clear cell renal cell carcinoma (ccRCC).

ccRCC accounts for 75% of total RCC incidence which increases worldwide and accounts for 2% of cancer diagnoses, affecting approximately 10/100000 in the United States and Western Europe [35]. Current treatment choice is largely driven by clinical trial inclusion criteria and guideline recommendations from the European Association of Urology [36], European Society of Medical Oncology [37] and American Society of Clinical Oncology [38] recommending first line treatment with combination immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICI) and tyrosine kinase inhibitors (TKI) therapy, or dual ICI for intermediate or poor risk disease. Despite these recommendations and the resultant improved survival benefit, still the response to treatment varies from individual to individual, complete response remains relatively rare, some patients develop significant adverse reactions to treatment and most patients eventually progress requiring a change in treatment [39].

Therefore, the greatest challenge is not only to gather more molecular or clinical information, but rather to better use and process the information that has already been gathered and is publicly available through the incorporation of pre-existing or newly developed foundation models. Despite a progress in AI-assisted noninvasive characterization of kidney tumors using CT imaging, better characterization of grading system [40], existence of clinical, pathological markers as well as genomic or transcriptomic signatures reported, potentially useful to guide treatment selection and predict response to systemic therapy, choosing the most optimal therapy with best treatment response at a patient-specific level is currently the biggest unmet need [41].

This is where the KATY project steps in developing a system which is interactively trained rather than being strictly programmed allowing for prediction without predefined rules and providing explainability to end users. The AI-assisted KATY Platform is built around the (i) KATY Holistic Neural Network (KATYHoNN) black-box model and the (ii) Distributed Knowledge Graph offering *post-hoc* explainability.

Datasets and ontologies

To build the KG for the KATYHoNN model we utilize two type of datasets:

(i) data from clinical trials evaluating the efficiency of targeted therapies, immunotherapies and combination of both,

(ii) publicly-available omics datasets for ccRCC patients.

We divided these dense and multi-modal datasets into "main" and "support" datasets. The "main dataset" makes use of (i) data from clinical trials and associated ontologies to address the question on the treatment effectiveness measured for each antitumor drug and estimate response-to-treatment metrics (i.e. tumor shrinkage, overall response rate (ORR), progression-free survival (PFS), and overall survival (OS)).

The "support dataset" makes use of (i) publicly-available omics datasets and associated ontologies to predict features which are not directly linked to response-to-therapy.

Both data types will be integrated into a knowledge graph through a network of ontologies, to offer comprehensive, interconnected and explainable representation of treatment effectiveness and influencing factors for a single patient (**Fig.1**).

Fig.1 Knowledge Graph construction and design. The Knowledge Graph is built using techniques of Ontology Matching and Semantic Annotation over renal cell carcinoma ontologies and KATY datasets stored in the data lake (the Knowledge Graph is stored in a GraphDB instance that supports fast loading, querying and visualization of the graph) (1). Upon development, the Knowledge Graph can be used as a source of knowledge-enriched features for the AI system (2). The outcomes of the AI-supported system can refine the Knowledge Graph (3). The data and outcomes as represented in the Knowledge Graph can be used to support explanation generation (4). Querying and visualizing the Knowledge Graph is supported by intelligent graphical user interfaces to present explanations to end-users.

KATY model

The KATY model deployed on the KATY Platform consists of sub-networks that are trained using data from clinical trials and omics data for ccRCC patients and also more widely available -omics data, for example T-cell antigen landscapes published across over 2300 published samples. Sub-division of the KATYHoNN model into sub-networks (trained either on specific omics dataset or on all omics datasets together) makes the realization of the final model easier and more precise, as each component is trained for a specific task and can be easily handled in the event of errors or changes.

This training strategy also mitigates the missing data problem, where there may be sufficient data for a specific task but insufficient data for all tasks combined. In case of insufficient data for model training, data from different cancer types can be used to pre-train specific sub-networks which can then be *transferred* to the ccRCC model. With this approach referred to as transfer learning, the KATYHoNN model can exploit future datasets enabling real-time training of the entire model. In this way the KATYHoNN model is easily modifiable, as at the same time, it is possible to add new components within the KATYHoNN model and modify the existing ones by deleting or linking them. The results from the KATYHoNN model deployed onto a dedicated KATY Platform and supported with the KG will allow physicians to predict survival/response to therapy when uploading patient's test results (**Fig. 2**).

Fig.2 General representation of the KATY Holistic Neural Network model (KATYHoNN). The KATYHoNN model input leverages publicly-available datasets for

ccRCC patients and data from clinical trials evaluating the efficiency of therapies. The heart of the model is composed of individual sub-networks for which the input is available omics data and clinical patient data. The sub-networks can be trained either on: (i) singular specific task (e.g. either genomics or transcriptomics or proteomics or RNA-Seq data) via transfer learning (**b**), or (ii) all tasks together (patients data evaluating the efficiency of therapies) via multi-task learning (**a**) to compile the general network. The result of a multi-task learning (a) is prediction of response-to-therapy, while the results from transfer learning (b) is prediction of other features not directly related to treatment choice. The KATYHoNN model deployed on a dedicated KATY Platform will allow a physician to upload a patient's test results and gain the best treatment recommendation in parallel with KG-driven explanation based on which features such a treatment was proposed and what the survival rate for that patient is.

Legal compliance

The KATY project ensures that the development and usage of the KATY Platform, as well as the use and re-use of the data generated and collected in the KATY project, is conducted in accordance with binding legal provisions. The project monitors and addresses the requirements set forth in the EU legal acts concerning (personal) data protection (especially with regard to special categories of data, i.e. data concerning health and genetic data), AI and data governance. Once the data protection and privacy principles have been identified, technical solutions such as data access management, encryption, cryptographic components, pseudonymisation and, where achievable, anonymisation of data, data minimisation, secure storage of data and secure data transfer, have been included in the design of the KATY Platform allowing for the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)-compliant processing of the data and usage of the platform.

Multi-tiered technology in AI-assisted explainable systems

Realizing the vision of an AI-empowered Personalized Medicine in the clinical workflow is challenging and needs a multi-tiered approach in order to develop a decision support system capable of handling the complexity of multi-modal data simultaneously being adaptable to new knowledge and constantly changing treatment guidelines.

Multi-tiered system technology refers to a layered (tiered) architectural approach that separates different functional components of layers, each assigned to distinct responsibilities and functionalities. This separation enhances modularity, scalability, and maintainability, making the system more robust and easier to manage. Such a modular system is composed of 3 tiers: (i) Presentation Tier (top layer), (ii) Application Tier (middle layer) and (iii) Data tier (bottom layer). Starting from the very bottom tier, the Data Tier is responsible for data secure storage, retrieval and integration between different sources. It generally includes (i) structured databases such as electronic health records (EHRs) and patient information, (ii) unstructured data such as treatment histories and medical imaging data, (iii) domain-specific knowledge repositories such as current clinical guidelines, protocols and best practices. Data under the Data Tier module should follow FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to help ensure that the data is managed in a way that maximizes its value and usability. The Application Tier serves as the core functional layer, responsible for processing input data, applying algorithms, and generating data-based recommendations. It utilizes the system's rules and guidelines to aid decision-making and ensures seamless data flow between various system components. The Presentation Tier provides graphical user interfaces (GUIs) through web applications or mobile interfaces and is responsible for interacting with doctors, researchers and healthcare professionals. It contains dashboards, graphs, and other visualizations to provide explainability-driven recommendations. It also allows end-users to input data, query knowledge quickly and conveniently, and receive feedback. The separation between 3 tiers facilitates managing and maintenance of the whole system, so that changes in one tier (e.g., user interface updates) do not necessarily affect the other tiers [42,43].

This modular architecture offers: (i) system's scalability by allowing for both horizontal (adding more servers to manage increased data loads) and vertical (involves upgrading existing servers with more memory, storage, or processing power) scaling, ensuring efficient handling of higher loads and numerous requests without slowing down or crashing the system; (ii) flexibility by updating or replacing of each tier component independently, ensuring that the addition of a new data source can be easily integrated into the data tier without any harm to the presentation or application tiers; (iii) enhanced security attributed separately to each tier, e.g. data encryption and access controls can be applied at the data tier, while user authentication and authorization can be managed at the presentation tier; (iv) improved performance (efficiency) ensured by load balancing (even distribution of the workload across multiple servers or components preventing from overwhelming with too many tasks); (iv) interoperability by ensuring seamless integration with existing healthcare systems and data repositories; (v) usability provided by the user-friendly interface and visualization tools helping healthcare providers make informed decisions quickly.

Multi-tiered technology is commonly utilized in information technology (IT) branches such as web development, enterprise softwares, finance, banking and many others. We believe that multi-tiered technology which revolutionized core business processes across companies, ensured secure and efficient handling of transactions, could also be step-by-step introduced into the biomedical domain and in the end revolutionize patients' healthcare system as it did in various IT branches. To date, there is no multi-tiered technological system supporting doctors' decisions in the precision medicine field. With respect to WFO precision medicine system, we might suspect that WFO system architecture could be similar to the multi-tiered system design (details are not provided by IBM) described above, however it did not address usability, information standard and interoperability. Additionally, because it incorporated the expert opinions (alongside available guidelines) from a tertiary hospital in the USA, it hindered the localized use of WFO in other countries.

Barriers and challenges in developing AI-assisted systems

Within the multi-tiered technology, the implementation of AI-explainable decision support systems into medical practice is hindered by technical barriers across all three tiers.

The data tier level presents significant challenges related to data availability and quality, lack of standards to catalog the data, lack of access to clinical records extracted from EHR, lack of standardization of repositories. Given the complexity of the biomedical data, with many missing data within, we should build ontologies and knowledge graph-based semantic similarity capturing different perspectives of entity representation to express domain-specific knowledge. Another hurdle at the data tier level is constantly changing clinical guidelines, and costs associated with curation of databases to ensure their validity (adherence between existing guidelines and clinical decision-support system).

Feeding the system with updated patient information ensures that clinicians have access to the latest knowledge and research findings. This is crucial to keep functionality of the Application Tier which aims at offering valid treatment recommendations. To explain the decisions, one requires an integration between the knowledge-based Data Tier and the model-based Application Tier ensuring the possibility of querying the system. Integrating these tiers would develop a transparent decision-making system and would be a milestone in earning the trust and acceptance of doctors. Ensuring knowledge-based explainability within a domain-specific field of cancer would facilitate the process of building interpretability and gaining new knowledge.

The greatest challenge at the Presentation Tier is to design interfaces that effectively communicate complex medical information and recommendations in a clear, intuitive, and user-friendly manner. A dashboard summarizing patient's information and interactive visualizations of tumor progression with survival prediction are those ways of presenting patients' status which attract the human eye. Being able to input patient data into the system and view treatment recommendations accompanied with visual analytics is a basic functionality that should be provided by the clinical decision support system. Equally important is to give patients permission to log in to the system and keep track of their treatment plan being able to communicate with the healthcare team.

Apart from challenges requiring a multi-faceted approach involving technological innovation and human-centered design, one should also consider privacy and security of the data. Explainable AI systems rely on vast quantities of patient data, underscoring the critical importance of data protection, especially concerning sensitive information such as genetic and health-related data. Consequently, regulations like the European Union's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other global and national data protection laws impose strict controls on the processing, sharing, and storage of personal data, including limitations on the volume of data processed.

Anonymizing or pseudonymizing biomedical data presents challenges in ensuring that all potentially identifiable information is effectively removed and that re-identification risks are minimized (Gymrek et al. 2013, Naveed et al. 2015, Rocher et al. 2019, Boonen et al. 2019). One of the key means that ensures GDPR-compliant data processing is appropriate compliance with data protection principles (Article 5 GDPR), application of technical and security measures, which ensures a level of security appropriate to the risk of the processing

(Article 32 GDPR), as well as the implementation of solutions responding to the data protection by design and by default requirements (Article 25 GDPR).

To ensure the appropriate protection of sensitive data, both technical and organizational measures must be implemented. Among the technical measures are data access management, encryption using cryptographic components, pseudonymization, and where possible, anonymization of data. Additionally, data minimization, secure storage, and secure data transfer must also be considered.

The AI-supported decision system must adhere to GDPR requirements by defining roles in data processing through joint controllership agreements among developers. Datasets should be managed by designated developers, shared in pseudonymized or anonymized forms via specific cloud infrastructure. Sensitive data should be encrypted during transmission and remains encrypted except during processing tasks. GDPR principles should be embedded into the design of the system to ensure compliant handling of data and usage of the system. Upon system development, one should recognize the data protection concerns ensuring their compatibility with the ethical norms and legal requirements.

Even if all technological barriers are addressed and data privacy and security are ensured, several challenges still remain. These include system maintenance, the need for internal and external validation of AI-supported systems, and the local feasibility of recommendations. It is crucial to adapt the system to context-specific requirements and limitations, integrate clinicians' and patients' preferences, and ensure interoperability with other data sources like EHRs [44].

Perspectives

As society increasingly adopts artificial intelligence, we are at a pivotal moment in medical practice where integrating AI-supported decision-making systems can make knowledge easily accessible to clinicians and the medical research community. This could one day lead to AI-supported personalized treatment guidelines and certainly will impact precision medicine in cancer. Biomedical AI is not only transforming medicine but also changing the mindset of how biomedical research is conducted. Previously, the engineering aspect of computational medicine was less emphasized in biomedical research, but now, leveraging state-of-the-art technology requires researchers to integrate engineering principles into their work. By integrating AI into biomedical research and clinical settings, we are witnessing a shift towards more precise, replicable, and rapid advancements in medical science.

To realize this vision within cancer research and clinical practice, we need to adopt principles from the technology sector and integrate them into healthcare research and clinical settings, creating an adaptable platform capable of replacing outdated practices with new and emerging standards of care. Over the next several years, we anticipate the establishment of digital medicine centers that will invest in human resources, assembling well-connected medical, IT, and research teams to make these advancements a reality. Upon development of biomedical decision-support systems, new professionals in this sector will evolve whose responsibility will be to adjust medical guidelines to accommodate constantly evolving treatments, and build disease-oriented knowledge models in a domain-specific field.

Continuous feedback on the quality of recommendations and patient status is essential. With real-time explainable treatment recommendations, the next step would be to link post-treatment (follow-up) data of individual patients with potential side effects and drug interactions, personalized to their medical history and current medications. To fully leverage AI-supported systems linked to knowledge-based models, we must start collecting omics data for each patient within the healthcare system while simultaneously training and motivating doctors on how and why to use these systems in their daily practice. In the future, those who incorporate AI-supported tools into their routine will probably replace those who do not.

It is important to encourage the transparent communication of the issue that the areas of greatest unmet need for biomedical AI solutions, such as personalized cancer treatment, are extremely complex and data sparse. Effective communication with both funding institutions and the broader stakeholder community is valuable for identifying the most feasible and realistic architectures to address the problem to overcome the hype. Valuable clinical trial data and -omic data is hidden by numerous legal agreements, creating a significant barrier to integrating and making this data accessible for AI systems. In these clinical trial contexts, patient health is prioritized over data volume, leading to the use of simpler, transparent models developed to address specific clinical questions. A modern approach may involve leveraging foundation models—large, pre-trained AI models for specific data types that can be fine-tuned for various tasks—and using them as black-box models with post-hoc

explainability rooted in visual representation and feature relevance. Despite efforts to build AI-supported decision systems, a systematic study of explanations for decisions within disease-specific domains is still missing. The explanations offered by AI decision-support systems must provide understandable and conceptually coherent knowledge. Only then can AI models provide transparent, human-interpretable explanations of AI-assisted diagnosis and treatment recommendations, facilitating their adoption in real clinical settings. Building on how the AI model explains its predictions is important for gaining trust from the medical community and establishing domain-expert interpretation and inference grounded in current medical findings. Another missing aspect refers to leveraging knowledge from publicly available omics data repositories and building knowledgeable databases within the context of specific cancer types. Addressing these gaps in explanation structure and knowledge leveraging is essential for advancing knowledge-based model development driving explainable AI.

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Author contributions

EDW and JA wrote the article and performed the literature search, FMZ and MM conceptualized the model and revised the work, AP and FMZ developed the figures, AL, SS, MS, DH, CB, CP revised the part related to therapy of ccRCC and Knowledge Graph, KB drafted the legal aspect of the study, the rest of authors revised the work and approved the final manuscript.

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Competing Interests

All authors declare no financial or non-financial competing interests.

Figure Captions

Fig.1 Knowledge Graph construction and design. The Knowledge Graph is built using techniques of Ontology Matching and Semantic Annotation over renal cell carcinoma ontologies and KATY datasets stored in the data lake (the Knowledge Graph is stored in a GraphDB instance that supports fast loading, querying and visualization of the graph) (1). Upon development, the Knowledge Graph can be used as a source of knowledge-enriched features for the AI system (2). The outcomes of the AI-supported system can be integrated back into the Knowledge Graph (3). The data and outcomes as represented in the Knowledge Graph can be used to support explanation generation (4). Querying and visualizing the Knowledge Graph is supported by intelligent graphical user interfaces to present explanations to end-users.

Fig.2 General representation of the KATY Holistic Neural Network model (KATYHoNN). The KATYHoNN model input leverages publicly-available datasets for ccRCC patients and data from clinical trials evaluating the efficiency of therapies.

The heart of the model is composed of individual sub-networks for which the input is available omics data and clinical patient data. The sub-networks can be trained either on: (i) singular specific task (e.g. either genomics or transcriptomics or proteomics or RNA-Seq data) via transfer learning (**b**), or (ii) all tasks together (patients data evaluating the efficiency of therapies) via multi-task learning (**a**) to compile the general network. The result of a multi-task learning (a) is prediction of response-to-therapy, while the results from transfer learning (b) is prediction of other features not directly related with treatment choice. The KATYHoNN model deployed on a dedicated KATY Platform will allow a physician to upload a patient's test results and gain the best treatment recommendation in parallel with explanation (KG-driven) based on which features such a treatment was proposed and what the survival rate for that patient is.